

Supplementary Information for:

Schönauer, M., Prinz, R., Väättäinen, K., Astrup, R., Pszenny, D., Lindeman, H., et al. (2022). Spatio-temporal prediction of soil moisture using soil maps, topographic indices and SMAP retrievals. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 102730. doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2022.102730

Supplementary Table S1. Several variables, as available from European Commission - Joint Research Centre (2004) *European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC)*. Available from: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> [Accessed 19 August 2021], that were considered for modelling of soil moisture content. * indicates variables which were kept as input after checking for redundancy and co-variation.

Data field name	Description
*AGLIM1	Code of the most important limitation to agricultural use of the STU
*AGLIM1NNI	Dominant limitation to agricultural use (without no information)
*AGLIM2	Code of a secondary limitation to agricultural use of the STU
*AGLIM2NNI	Secondary limitation to agricultural use (without no information)
*ALT	ELEVATION
ALT_MAX	100 m class maximum altitudes
ALT_MIN	100 m class minimum altitudes
*ATC	Accumulated temperature class
*AWC_SUB	Subsoil available water capacity
*AWC_TOP	Topsoil available water capacity
*BS_SUB	Base saturation of the subsoil
*BS_TOP	Base saturation of the topsoil
*CEC_SUB	Subsoil cation exchange capacity
*CEC_TOP	Topsoil cation exchange capacity
*CRUST	Soil crusting class
DGH	Depth to a gleyed horizon
DIFF	Soil profile differentiation
DIMP	Depth to an impermeable layer
*DR	Depth to rock
*EAWCSUB	Subsoil easily available water capacity
*EAWCTOP	Topsoil easily available water capacity
*ERODIBI	Soil erodibility class
FAO85FU	Full soil code of the STU from the 1974 (modified CEC 1985) FAO-UNESCO Soil Legend
FAO85FU_CL	Confidence level for FAO85FU
FAO90FU	Full soil code of the STU from the 1990 FAO-UNESCO Soil Legend
FAO90FU_CL	Confidence level for FAO90FU
*HG	Hydrogeological class
*IL	Code for the presence of an impermeable layer within the soil profile of the STU
*MIN	Profile mineralogy
*MIN_SUB	Subsoil mineralogy
*MIN_TOP	Topsoil mineralogy
*OC_TOP	Topsoil organic carbon content
*PARMADO	Code for dominant parent material of the STU

PARMADO_CL	Confidence level for PARMADO
*PARMASE	Code for secondary parent material of the STU
PARMASE_CL	Confidence level for PARMASE
PD_SUB	Subsoil packing density
*PD_TOP	Topsoil packing density
PEAT	Peat
*PHYSCHI	Physi-chemical factor of soil crusting & erodibility
*PMH	Parent material hydrogeological type
ROO	Depth class of an obstacle to roots within the STU
*SLOPE_DOM	Dominant slope class of the STU
*SLOPE_SEC	Secondary slope class of the STU
STR_SUB	Subsoil structure
*STR_TOP	Topsoil structure
*TD	Rule inferred subsoil texture
*TEXT	Dominant surface textural class (completed from dominant STU)
*TEXTCRU	Textural factor of soil crusting
TEXTDEPCHG	Depth class to a textural change of the dominant and/or secondary surface texture of the STU
*TEXTERO	Textural factor of soil erodibility
TEXTSRFDOM	Dominant surface textural class of the STU
*TEXTSRFSEC	Secondary surface textural class of the STU
*TEXTSUBDOM	Dominant sub-surface textural class of the STU
*TEXTSUBSEC	Secondary sub-surface textural class of the STU
USE	Regrouped land use class
*USE_DOM	Code for dominant land use of the STU
USE_SEC	Code for secondary land use of the STU
*VS	Volume of stones
*WM1	Code for normal presence and purpose of an existing water management system in agricultural land on more than 50% of the STU
*WM2	Code for the type of an existing water management system
*WR	Dominant annual average soil water regime class of the soil profile of the STU
*WRBFU	Full soil code of the STU from the World Reference Base (WRB) for Soil Resources
*ZMAX	Maximum elevation above sea level of the STU (in metres)
ZMIN	Minimum elevation above sea level of the STU (in metres)
